

Development of artificial pseudo-subjective systems

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

As you know, the development of programming methods is allowing development of software and hardware suitable for many purposes. However, there are numerous and well known limitations that cannot be overcome by programming.

For example, millions of people around the world needing assistance, but no one can fulfill the quest. No one can design self-driving vehicles which could meet the requirements of the fifth category. It is impossible to develop fully functional robots for housekeeping, surgery, education and many other duties where a person could function more or less successfully, but robots can do these only partially.

2. Aim

Proposing of a new approach for designing artificial systems capable to develop themselves and accruing a professional skill, without needs be programmed for performing the required functions. For example, a robot driver, designed in accordance with the our concept, will be able to pass driving tests, operate any vehicle, perform logistical and maintenance operations.

3. Conception

The formulated conception is allow engineers of ALL choose a finite set of operational spaces, reword functions and goals, where all and every situation possibly encountered by a system in future are covered. A prospective study was conducted in ALL over 12 month period in which we are going deep in motivational problems, safety and control units architecture development.

Additionally we are working on design of an energetically efficient locomotion system.

4. Results

We are planning to continue development of a control unit for a humanoid robot, which should adapt itself to a robots hardware and accumulating of its own subjective experience during interaction with environment, education and training.

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5. Conclusions

The way for development of pseudo-subjective systems is discovered, and, although there still many obstacles to be removed, that way will lead to development of artificial semi - live systems, capable to determine its own behavior in prematurely unknown for designers circumstances, and which will be absolutely safe for biological form of life, because they will did not have own egoistic interests.

6. Keywords

Programming; Limitation; Autonomy; Professional skill; Efficiency.

Author biography

Michael Zeldich Michael Zeldich gets his education in Kharkov Polytechnic Academy and working as engineer for solving non standard problems. Michael Zeldich has few diplomas granting his rights as author. One of his designs of consumer product gets second place recognition in entire USSR competition. Some of his technological solutions are still in use during more than 50 years.